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Sharopova Mamurahon Uzaqovna

Andijan Region Buloqboshi district teacher of biology at
school 33
Uzbekistan

USE OF MODERN TECHNOLOGIES IN BIOLOGY TEACHERS

Abstract: This article presents ideas on conducting lessons on the use of modern educational technologies by biology teachers.

Key words: Modern technology, problem situation, creative thinking, critical thinking, critical thinking, logical thinking.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada biologiya o'qituvchilari tomonidan zamonaviy ta'lim texnologiyalaridan foydalanish bo'yicha darslar o'tkazish bo'yicha fikrlar keltirilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: Zamonaviy texnologiya, muammoli vaziyat, ijodiy fikrlash, tanqidiy fikrlash, tanqidiy fikrlash, mantiqiy fikrlash.

Аннотация: В данной статье представлены идеи по проведению уроков по использованию современных образовательных технологий учителями биологии.

Ключевые слова: Современные технологии, проблемная ситуация, творческое мышление, критическое мышление, критическое мышление, логическое мышление.

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Modern pedagogical technologies, teaching methods determine the activities of teachers and students in the educational process, how to organize and conduct the teaching process, and what actions students should perform in this process.

The main form of organizing the educational process is the lesson. Currently, various non-traditional forms of lessons are being introduced. Such classes develop the student's creative abilities, strengthen his intellectual potential, expand his scientific worldview, and develop the skills and abilities to quickly and fully accept every new thing. The use of modern technologies during the lesson arouses interest in scientific research in students, develops creativity and creativity. As a result, acquired knowledge, skills and abilities are applied in practical activities, the quality of learning increases. For this, the teacher must be skilled and plan the lesson according to the content of the topics, and make all students work actively and consciously during the training. Therefore, chemistry teachers, like all science teachers, constantly use modern pedagogical technologies and interactive methods in their classes, which helps to increase the effectiveness of education. For this, based on the nature of the subject, the choice of modern pedagogical technologies suitable for the subject and successful use in the lessons depends on the skill of the future chemistry teacher.

Chemistry education is a complex and very important stage: giving a good (quality) lesson is not an easy task even for an experienced teacher. In this regard, the following requirements are set for modern chemistry classes:

1. Achieving the goals of the lesson should be clearly oriented.
2. The scientific nature of the content, that is, the theoretically correct explanation of the main concepts, laws and evidence of chemistry to the students.
3. Let the high ideological and political level of the lesson serve to form a scientific worldview in students.
4. To provide education taking into account the interdependence of subjects.
5. Logical thinking of students, use of all possibilities of content and teaching methods for the problematic system of the educational process, which is one of the most important conditions for the development of their creative abilities.
6. Combining different methods of teaching that ensure the suitability and compatibility of teaching at a level of sufficient difficulty that corresponds to the purpose of the lesson and the content of the educational material, using all types of chemical experiments and a set of teaching tools.
7. To increase the weight of independent work of students in the lesson, to combine frontal, group and individual work of students.
8. All parts of the lesson should be compatible with each other, they should be in

accordance with the main didactic purpose, and the study time should be used wisely.

9. In the lesson, there should be a quiet work environment based on mutual trust and sincerity of the teacher and the student.

In order to form students' motivation for science, we can show several technologies in teaching the 9th grade chemistry lesson as an example of the "Manganese" topic.

When checking homework. Assessment technique is used to repeat the previous topic. For this, students are given the following assessment task. The new topic starts with the game "Spy 007" below. For this, readers are referred to the following table. Students are

given the task of finding the word hidden in the cells using the given numbers.

The chemical properties of manganese are explained using the "Fish Skeleton" method. Students write the corresponding reaction equations independently.

"Cluster" method is used to strengthen the topic.

"Problematic situation" method is a method aimed at forming students' skills in analyzing the causes and consequences of problematic situations and finding their solutions.

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